

GREENGAGE

ENGAGING CITIZENS - MOBILIZING TECHNOLOGY - DELIVERING GREEN DEAL

Evaluation and Impact Assessment Methodology and Design 2

Work Package 6, Deliverable D6.2

AWAITING VALIDATION FOR THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION

Evaluation and Impact Assessment Methodology and Design 2

Work package 6, Deliverable D6.2

Please refer to this report as follows:

Gebetsroither-Geringer, E., Khan Z., I., Soomro, K. (2025). Evaluation and Impact Assessment Methodology and Design 2. Deliverable D6.2 of the Horizon Europe project GREENGAGE.

Project information	
Project name:	GREENGAGE – Innovative governance, environmental observations and digital solutions in support of the Green Deal
Grant Agreement No.	101086530
Start date:	01/01/2023
Duration:	36 months
Coordinator:	AIT Austrian Institute of Technology Giefinggasse 4, 1210 Vienna, Austria
Contact:	Jan Peters-Anders, Research Engineer
	Funded by the European Union GA n° 101086530.
Deliverable details	
Description:	Deliverable description
Version:	Final
Dissemination level:	PU (Public)
Due date:	31/12/2025
Submission:	31/12/2025
Lead:	AIT Austrian Institute of Technology
Author(s):	Gebetsroither-Geringer, E. (AIT), Austria Khan Z. (UWE) UK, Soomro, K. (UWE), UK

Legal Disclaimer

All information in this document is provided "as is" and no guarantee or warranty is given that the information is fit for any particular purpose. The user, therefore, uses the information at its sole risk and liability. For the avoidance of all doubts, the European Commission has no liability in respect of this document, which is merely representing the authors' view.

Users wishing to reuse material from this work that is attributed to a third party, such as tables, figures or images, are responsible for determining whether permission is needed for that reuse and for obtaining permission from the copyright holder. The risk of claims resulting from infringement of any third party-owned component in the work rests solely with the user.

© 2025 by GREENGAGE Consortium

AWAITING VALIDATION FOR THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION

Table of Contents

Content

1	GREENGAGE summary.....	2
2	Object of the Deliverable.....	3
3	Introduction	4
4	Evaluation approaches	5
4.1	CIM framework.....	5
4.2	Other evaluation methods and frameworks	6
4.2.1	Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) model	6
4.2.2	Open framework for evaluating citizen science	6
4.2.3	Guide on building and evaluating environmental citizen science by NHM.....	8
4.2.4	GREENGAGE approach inspired from literature	8
4.2.5	Action Framework a Methodology to Measure Impact in GREENGAGE.....	9
4.3	Alignment between CIM and the ACTION Methodologies.....	12
5	GREENGAGE CIM and Tools & Methods.....	13
5.1	GREENGAGE Evaluation Process	15
5.2	Workflow of the CIM development	17
5.3	Examples of Indicators	19
6	Lessons Learned & Recommendations	26
	Annex-A: Template for the Evaluation Design	27
	Annex-B: List of current KPIs	28
	Annex-C: List of Criteria and Sub-Criteria	30
	References	32

List of Figures

Figure 1: Structure of project GREENGAGE.....	2
Figure 2: Evaluation Methodology: Criteria-Indicator-Metrics - 2	5
Figure 3: CIM2 methodology: An Example.	6
Figure 4. Measuring impact in GREENGAGE for citizens and managers adapted from the ACTION framework © GREENGAGE.....	10
Figure 5: Recipe to measure the impact which is adapted in GREENGAGE from [8].....	11
Figure 6: CIM and ACTION conceptual mapping	12
Figure 7: GREENGAGE Evaluation Process.....	15

List of Tables

Table 1: Criteria for the three core dimensions of the citizen science evaluation framework.	7
Table 2: Mapping UTAUT2 Constructs to CIM Criteria.....	9
Table 3: Impact evaluation to summarise who should respond, what and when.	11
Table 4: The following table shows some of KPIs. (O is Outcome, I is Impact)	13
Table 5: A subset of criteria for Quality in Use and Product Quality.	13
Table 6: Criterion, Sub-criterion, Indicator matrix.....	14

Table 6: Template for the evaluation design for each Indicator.....	27
Table 7: Entire List of KPIs.....	28
Table 8: Additional list of Criterion and Sub-Criterion.....	30

List of Acronyms

CIM	Criteria Indicator Metrics
UTAUT2	Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology v2
CO	Citizen Observatory
COb	Citizen Observer
EO	Earth Observation
GEOSS	Global Earth Observation System of Systems
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
FP6 or FP7	Framework Program 6, Framework Program 7

Glossary

Citizen Observatory	According to the EU project WeObserve, “Citizen Observatories (COs) are community-based environmental monitoring and information systems, that invite individuals to share observations, typically via mobile phone or the web. Throughout these activities citizens become able to participate in environmental management/local governance.”
Outcome	The expected effects, over the medium term, of projects supported under a given topic. The results of a project should contribute to these outcomes, fostered in particular by the dissemination and exploitation measures. This may include the uptake, diffusion, deployment, and/or use of the project’s results by direct target groups. Outcomes generally occur during or shortly after the end of the project. ¹
Impact	Wider long-term effects on society (including the environment), the economy and science, enabled by the outcomes of R&I investments (long term). It refers to the specific contribution of the project to the work programme expected impacts described in the destination. Impacts generally occur sometime after the end of the project. ¹
Results	What is generated during the project implementation. This may include, for example, know-how, innovative solutions, algorithms, proof of feasibility, new business models, policy recommendations, guidelines, prototypes, demonstrators, databases and datasets, trained researchers, new infrastructures, networks, etc. Most project results (inventions, scientific works, etc.) are ‘Intellectual Property’, which may, if appropriate, be protected by formal ‘Intellectual Property Rights’. ¹
Marginalized groups	“Different groups of people within a given culture, context and history at risk of being subjected to multiple discrimination due to the interplay of different personal characteristics or grounds, such as sex, gender, age, ethnicity, religion or belief,

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/experts/standard-briefing-slides-for-experts_he_en.pdf last Accessed: 22 Dezember 2025

	health status, disability, sexual orientation, gender identity, education or income, or living in various geographic localities” (European Institute of Gender Equality) ²
Citizen Science	“In Citizen Science, a broad network of people collaborates. Participants provide experimental data and facilities for researchers, raise new questions and co-create a new scientific culture. While they add value, volunteers acquire new learning and skills and gain a deeper understanding of the scientific work in appealing ways. As a result of this open, networked and transdisciplinary scenario, science-society-policy interactions are improved, leading in turn to a more democratic research, based on evidence and informed decision-making” (Socientize consortium, 2014, p. 10).

AWAITING VALIDATION FOR THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION

² <https://eige.europa.eu/publications-resources/thesaurus/terms/1175> , last Accessed: 22 Dezember 2025

Executive summary (publishable)

This report presents GREENGAGE evaluation and impact assessment methodology that is inspired from Criteria Indicators and Metrics (CIM) method used in different EU funded projects. The evaluation process consists of Design, Co-Development and Co-Verification, Implementation and Reporting stages. This report covers the Design and Co-Development and Co-Verification stages.

As the focus of GREENGAGE evaluation is mainly on the benefits and usability of GREENGAGE CO approach, GREEN Engine and overall outcomes of Piloting, using the CIM method several sub-criteria indicators metrics and associated questions are identified collaboratively with GREENGAGE partners.

This report provides indicators and metrics not only for WP6 tasks but also for tasks in other WPs (WP4, WP5, WP7). This is extended version of the D6.1 Evaluation and Impact Assessment Methodology and Design 1. Based on the lessons learned from the 1st cycle of piloting, this version is extended with refined and more meaningful list of indicators and metrics. Furthermore, specific methods of evaluation, such as in-system statistics, interviews, surveys, sentiment analysis, etc. are also described in this report. Additionally, a new method called 'ACTION Framework' was investigated and adapted for impact assessment. It was observed that the method is quite aligned with the CIM approach. This report is the final version of the list of indicators and metrics. The outputs for these indicators are covered in other WP5 and WP6 deliverables.

Related documents

All GREENGAGE deliverables that are related to this document are listed below and are available at the GREENGAGE website <https://www.greengage-project.eu/knowledge-base/deliverables/>.

Deliverable D4.5 – GREENGAGE Experiment and Monitoring System and Manual 1

Deliverable D6.1 - GREENGAGE Evaluation and Impact Assessment Methodology and Design 1

1 GREENGAGE summary

The pan-European Innovation Action, funded under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme, aimed to promote innovative governance processes, and tried to help public authorities in shaping their climate mitigation and adaptation policies. To achieve this aim, the GREENGAGE project leveraged citizens' participation and equipped them with innovative digital solutions that shall transform citizen's engagement and cities' effectiveness in delivering the European Green Deal objectives for carbon neutral cities.

Focusing on mobility, air quality, and healthy living, the aim was to inspire citizens to observe and co-create their cities by sensing their urban environments. The idea was to complement, validate, and enrich information in authoritative data held by the public administrations and public agencies. This was facilitated by engaging with citizens to co-create green initiatives and to develop Citizen Observatories (CO). In GREENGAGE, Citizen Observatories were and are a place where pilot cities co-examine environmental issues integrating novel bottom-up processes with top-down perspectives. This provides the basis to co-create and co-design innovative solutions to monitor environmental problems at ground level with the help of citizens.

With two interrelated project dimensions, the project aimed to enhance intelligence applied to city decision-making processes and governance by engaging with citizen observations integrated with Copernicus, Global Earth Observation System of Systems GEOSS, in-situ, and socio-economic intelligence, and by delivering innovative governance models based on novel toolboxes of decision-making methodologies and technologies.

The Citizens Observatory campaigns were deployed and fully demonstrated in 5 pilot engagements in selected European cities and regions including: Bristol (the United Kingdom), Copenhagen (Denmark), Turano Valley (Italy), Gerace (Italy) and the region of North Brabant (the Netherlands). These innovation pilots aimed to highlight the need for smart city governance by promoting citizen engagement, co-creation, as well as gathering new data which should complement existing datasets and evidence-based decision and policymaking.

Figure 1: Structure of project GREENGAGE.

2 Object of the Deliverable

This deliverable documents the work and results from Task 6.1 Evaluation and Impact Assessment Methodology and Design during the project. This contains a description of the used CIM and ACTION method and other related citizen science evaluation approaches. Furthermore, the aim is to present the evaluation process and design of the evaluation, the framework that was used in GREENGAGE, and how this was applied and further adapted from D6.1, within the second phase of the project. This deliverable presents the final version of the framework with selected criteria indicators and metrics.

3 Introduction

Evaluation and impact assessment is an integral part of the GREENGAGE project, and a full work package is allocated for this purpose. Before we elaborate the evaluation approach for the GREENGAGE project in detail, we would like to discuss what is meant by evaluation in the GREENGAGE project. Shapiro defines evaluation and impact as:

***Evaluation** is the comparison of actual impacts against strategic plans. It looks at original objectives, at what was accomplished and how it was accomplished. It can be formative, that is taking place during the life of a project or organization, with the intention of improving the strategy or way of functioning of the project or organisation. It can also be summative, drawing lessons from a completed project or an organisation that is no longer functioning (Shapiro J, Civicus [online]). Similarly, **Impact** tells you whether or not what you did made a difference to the problem situation you were trying to address. In other words, was your strategy useful? (Shapiro J, p3)*

The GREENGAGE evaluation and impact assessment focuses on the usability and benefits of the GREENGAGE assets which includes but is not limited to: the potential for policy use, contribution of citizen generated data to existing observation systems (e.g. GEOSS) and vice-versa, usefulness for Citizen Observatory (CO) methods, the GREENGAGE CO-enabling platform and piloting outcomes. The environmental, political, socio-economic, societal, and legal impacts of citizen observatories and collected in-situ data by means of the GREENGAGE project to the public administration and multi-disciplinary stakeholders including citizens was derived. Technical evaluation e.g., functional completeness, functional correctness, security, portability, reliability, performance etc. are not within the scope of WP6.

The emphasis in GREENGAGE was on formative evaluation carried out incrementally to provide regular, timely feedback, enabling learning and improving GREEN Engine features and piloting activities. This was done by engaging with evaluation users and stakeholders as well as by analysing the data captured through GREEN Engine. We also performed a summative user evaluation at the end of the project, mainly to assess and elaborate project development experiences, evaluation lessons learnt, pros and cons and make recommendations. Please note that these evaluation exercises was performed within a specified context that is directly related to the use cases defined by the piloting cities in Deliverable D2.2 and D2.3 – Use case and requirements analysis I & II, framework in D2.1 - GREENGAGE CO Methodological Framework, D2.4 and D2.5 - Governance Models I & II and assets developed in WP3, WP4 and WP5. Major GREENGAGE evaluation users and stakeholders include public administrations, general public/citizens, domain experts, policy and decision makers, planners, local businesses, technology experts, etc.

To systematically design and implement evaluation, the Criteria Indicators and Metrics (CIM) method is adapted, which has been previously used in various EU funded projects (Soomro K et al 2016). A collaborative approach, through workshops, was applied to demystify indicators and metrics and potential methods are identified. The first workshop was carried out during 2nd Progress and Consortium Meeting in Vienna (October 2023). This was followed by another online workshop in November 2023 where a Miro board was used to gather inputs from collaborators. In this extended version of the report, we cover an overview of the CIM method, our approach and the final status of the evaluation design including refined set of indicators & metrics. Additionally, this report presents ACTION Framework that is aligned with the CIM approach and provides a decent foundation for impact assessment task.

4 Evaluation approaches

4.1 CIM framework

To perform the evaluation in the GREENGAGE project, the Criteria Indices Metrics – Version 2 (CIM2) methodology has been selected which primarily defines the means to secure evaluation results as shown in Figure 2. To avoid confusion, we shall use CIM and CIM2 interchangeably. CIM2 is extended from the experience developed in the FP6 HUMBOLDT project (2011; Deliverable A19.6-D1 2010) and applied in the FP7 urbanAPI project (Soomro K et al 2016), FP7 DECUMANUS project (Ludlow D et al 2016) and H2020 smarticipate project (Soomro K et al 2018). Basically, this approach reflects on the design of the evaluation to be carried out. This approach defines a set of criteria based on specific aspects (e.g., project objectives, user functional and non-functional requirements), which need to be considered, for instance aspects related to usability, functionality, performance, efficiency, effectiveness, etc. Each criterion may have additional associated sub-criteria to address. Each sub-criterion is made operational by defining one or more indicators which address the evaluation criteria in question. To better understand the context of the evaluation for a particular aspect, each indicator is represented by one or more questions or statements. Also, for each indicator (and associated questions) some metrics are defined to judge whether the result is regarded as good or bad. For instance, “participatory governance” can be a criterion/sub-criterion for indicator “a wider citizen participation” that can be measured based on “number of citizen observers participated in the Citizen Observatory experiments” or “number of street hazards captured by the data collected by the citizens”.

Additionally, qualitative assessment is also included in CIM2 to enable evaluators to provide subjective (and/or objective) assessment mainly contributing to benefits, relevance and the overall impact of the GREENGAGE’s tools and applications. These qualitative outcomes can be in the form of subjective statements. For instance, “he data collected through CO provided new insights to public authorities in formulating policies and planning decisions.” Or “the scientific analysis of the data raised awareness about air quality that resulted in behaviour change”. Techniques like system usability scale (Brooke J, 1996) or its variations (Finstad K, 2010) or surveys may be utilised to give a global view of the subjective assessment.

Figure 2: Evaluation Methodology: Criteria-Indicator-Metrics - 2

As an example, we illustrate in Figure 3 ‘effectiveness’ as one of the main elements derived from ISO 25010 (ISO/IEC 25010:2011), selected as a main criterion and derived as three further sub-criteria which are defined as: ‘participatory governance’, ‘evidence-based decision making’ and ‘usefulness’. As an example, each sub-criterion identifies indicators, also considered as concerns to be evaluated. For example, participatory governance has more widespread citizen participation as an indicator. To define metrics for indicators, specific questions are defined which address the aspects to be evaluated for each indicator. For example, for the above indicator, relevant questions are ‘Have the CO increased the participation of citizens in environmental monitoring?’ and ‘Are diverse groups with protected characteristics involved in the data collection?’. These questions can have specific response options, each defined with quantitative and measurable weights.

Figure 3: CIM2 methodology: An Example.

Please note that depending upon the context and project objectives, a new criterion/sub-criterion can be defined, too, e.g., *benefits*, which may not exist in original characteristics of product in use and product quality of ISO25010. Annex-A provides an evaluation design template (Table 7) derived from CIM to be used for indicating overall criteria, indicators, metrics, and available resources.

4.2 Other evaluation methods and frameworks

4.2.1 Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) model

The UTAUT for impact assessment was developed by Venkatesh *et al.* (2003) (2012) to provide a framework to understand technologic acceptance holistically. The framework incorporated behavioural intention and use by suggesting that it determines the actual use of technology. According to the UTAUT model, the perceived likelihood of adopting the technology is dependent on four key constructs:

- performance expectancy,
- effort expectancy,
- social influence and
- facilitating conditions.

The framework was later extended to predict the acceptance of technology in an organisational context. In addition to the original constructs, UTAUT2 also adds hedonic motive, cost/perceived value, and habit. According to the theory, all the above constructs are moderated by age, gender, and experience.

4.2.2 Open framework for evaluating citizen science

Kieslinger *et al.* (2018) developed a holistic framework for evaluating a citizen science project focusing on both the process and outcome level. It is an open framework for evaluating diverse citizen science initiatives, based on an in-depth review of the characteristics and diversity of citizen science activities and current evaluation practices. The framework defines a few criteria and supporting questions for

three core dimensions: *scientific*, *participant* and *socio-ecological and economic*. Each dimension has separate criteria for the process and feasibility aspect as well as the outcome and impact aspect. The framework can be applied for:

- Strategic planning and funding assessments of citizen science proposals
- Monitoring progress during project duration and
- Assessing the possible impact at the end of a project.

For the purposes of this deliverable, we focus on the outcome and impacts aspect of all three dimensions as the process and feasibility aspects are out of scope for this deliverable. However, they will be considered in the overall project management (WP1) and other work packages of the project. The various criteria and supporting questions are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Criteria for the three core dimensions of the citizen science evaluation framework.

Indicator	Description
Scientific	
Scientific knowledge and publications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Does the project demonstrate an appropriate publication strategy, both in scientific and other media outlets? • Are citizen scientists recognised in publications and if so, can they participate in the dissemination of results?
New fields of research and research structures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Did the project generate new research questions, projects, or proposals? • Did the project contribute to any institutional or structural changes?
New knowledge resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Does the project ease access to traditional and local knowledge resources? • Does the project contribute to a better understanding of science in society?
Participant	
Knowledge, skills, competencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the learning outcomes with regards to new knowledge, skills, and competencies for the participants?
Science literacy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Does the project contribute to a better understanding of science? • Does the project contribute to a better understanding of the scientific topic?
Behaviour and ownership	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Does the project foster ownership amongst participants? • Does the project contribute to facilitating personal change in behaviour or political citizenship?
Motivation and engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Does the project raise motivation, self-esteem and empowerment amongst participants? • Are participants motivated to continue the project or involve in similar activities?
Socio-ecological and economic	
Collective capacity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Does the project contribute to the collective capacity of the participants in achieving common goals?

Political participation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Does the project stimulate political participation? • Does the project impact on policy processes and decision-making (e.g., through agenda-setting or data contribution for policy evaluation)?
Targeted interventions, control function	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Does the project include objectives that protect and enhance natural resources and/or foster environmental protection? • Does the project contribute to higher awareness, knowledge, and responsibility for the natural environment?
New technologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Does the project foster the use or development of new technologies?
Sustainability, social innovation practice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Does the project consider sustainability (environmental impact or sustained social relations) as part of the project plan? • Are the project results transferable to other contexts or organisations? • Does the project contribute to social, technical or political innovation?
Economic potential, market opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Does the project generate any economic impact or competitive advantages, (e.g., cost reduction, new job creation, new business models, etc.)? • Does the project foster co-operation for exploitation, (e.g., with social entrepreneurs)?

4.2.3 Guide on building and evaluating environmental citizen science by NHM

The Natural History Museum, London (NHM) and NERC Centre for Ecology & Hydrology for UK-EOF have published a guide to help set up citizen science projects to address issues of fragmentation, data access and a lack of strategic direction in environmental monitoring (Tweddle *et al.*, 2012). It provides basic step-by-step instructions to people who are already involved in citizen science projects as well as people who are new to citizen science. While the guide lays out the basic framework, it is lacking in both rigour and detail to be useful for a project of the magnitude and scale of GREENGAGE, particularly in terms of providing an evaluation framework. Therefore, this guide will not be considered for the purposes of this deliverable.

4.2.4 GREENGAGE approach inspired from literature

In the above sections, we have discussed three different frameworks for evaluating citizen science projects; UTAUT2, an open framework by Kieslinger *et al.* (2018) and the Natural History Museum guide on building and evaluating environmental citizen science. Of these, UTAUT2 provides an alternative perspective of the non-technical constructs that affect adoption and acceptance of technologies in practice. These constructs are already covered by indicators defined in the CIM2 methodology. In Table 2, we show the mapping between UTAUT2 constructs and CIM2 indicators for completeness. The open framework by Kieslinger *et al.* provides a more holistic framework that provides rigorous and fine-grained criteria to evaluate citizen science projects. This framework looks at the project from both the process perspective as well as the outcomes perspective for three core dimensions: *scientific*, *participant* and *socio-ecological and economic*. As WP6 is only concerned with the usefulness of the outcomes of the project, we will only focus on adapting that perspective from the framework. The process perspective is relevant for the overall project management (WP1) and other work packages. Finally, the Natural History Museum guide provides a very basic framework for setting up a citizen science project and will thus not be considered in this work package.

Table 2: Mapping UTAUT2 Constructs to CIM Criteria.

Construct	Description	CIM
Performance Expectancy	The degree to which an individual believes that using the system will help him or her to attain gains in job performance	Effectiveness, Efficiency, Context Coverage, Performance Efficiency
Effort expectancy	The degree of ease associated with the use of the system	Context Coverage, Functional Suitability, Interaction capability
Social Influence	The degree to which an individual perceives that important others believe he or she should use the new system	Effectiveness, Freedom from risk
Facilitating conditions	The degree to which an individual believes that an organisational and technical infrastructure exists to support the use of the system	Context coverage, Performance efficiency, Compatibility, Reliability, Security, Maintainability, Flexibility
Hedonic motivation	It is defined as the perceived enjoyment (fun or pleasure) derived from using technology. It plays an important role in determining technology acceptance and use	Satisfaction, Interaction capability
Cost	Consumers' trade-off between the perceived benefits of the applications and the monetary cost for using them	Efficiency
Habit	The extent to which people tend to perform behaviours automatically	Efficiency, Satisfaction

4.2.5 Action Framework a Methodology to Measure Impact in GREENGAGE

The European Commission funded ACTION project³ provides a methodology to measure the impact of a citizen science project. To measure the GREENGAGE project impacts, questionnaires were reviewed and adapted from The ACTION project and translated to all foreign languages of the GREENGAGE project (NL, DK, EN, IT). Once validated by pilot participants, these were administered either ex-ante, ex-post or both depending on the type of respondents (i.e., co-managers, co-participants) (see Table 3). The procedure was based on the ACTION methodology as can be seen below (see Figure 5 and Figure 6). In a glimpse, it can be observed how some dimensions were only evaluated by participants, other only by managers, and some of the impacts only had one iteration, while others have an ex-ante and ex-post approach. Many questionnaires were administered in the first iteration, and a refined form was used in the 2nd iteration of GREENGAGE piloting phases.

³ <https://actionproject.eu/>

Measuring approach in GREENGAGE

Figure 4. Measuring impact in GREENGAGE for citizens and managers adapted from the ACTION framework © GREENGAGE.

The impact assessment evaluates the various dimensions related to citizen science (see Deliverable D6.5 Annex-A for more detailed information about the relation with the KPIs). It categorizes impacts into six main areas: scientific, social, economic, political, environmental, and transformative. Each area is assessed through the perspectives of two primary respondents: co-managers, who oversee the project, and co-participants, who actively participate in it. The assessment can be conducted at two stages, ex-ante - prior to the project's initiation (i.e., the initiation of the thematic co-explorations and the use of the technology), or ex-post - after its completion, depending on the respondents (see Table 3). In the following, it is explained in detail the intentions behind of the evaluation of each impact.

Scientific Impact

In the Scientific Impact category, co-managers are responsible for evaluating the quantity and quality of new data generated, adherence to open data principles, and the visibility of research outputs across various platforms. They conduct assessments only in the ex-post phase, meaning they evaluate the outcomes after the project has been completed. Co-participants, on the other hand, contribute exclusively during the ex-post phase, sharing their experiences regarding their involvement in the research process and the knowledge they gain from it.

Social Impact

The Social Impact section focuses on community building and empowerment. Co-managers report on the number of citizen scientists engaged in project activities and their roles in participatory research. Similar to the Scientific Impact, managers conduct assessments only in the ex-post phase. Co-participants provide insights during the ex-ante and ex-post phase, reflecting on changes in their social capital, including bonding, bridging, and linking social relationships, as well as the establishment of new social connections.

Economic Impact

In the Economic Impact category, co-managers evaluate metrics such as job creation within the leading organization and the generation of new or improved products and services. They also consider the cost savings associated with volunteer engagement, conducting assessments solely in the ex-post phase. Co-participants report on any changes in their employment status or economic benefits resulting from their participation in the project, providing feedback exclusively during the ex-post phase.

Political Impact

For the Political Impact, both managers and citizens are actively involved in assessments during both the ex-ante and ex-post phases. Co-managers assess the number of new or modified policies that emerge from the project, as well as the extent of citizen engagement in political activities. Co-participants

reflect on their involvement in civic engagement and political groups, contributing valuable grassroots perspectives on the project's influence on political processes and community activism throughout both phases.

Environmental Impact

The Environmental Impact is measured through both direct and indirect effects. Co-managers evaluate improvements in air, water, and soil quality, conducting assessments only in the ex-post phase. Co-participants, however, provide feedback during both the ex-ante and ex-post phases, reporting on their perceptions of environmental changes and the project's effectiveness in promoting sustainability before and after its implementation.

Transformative Impact

Finally, the Transformative Impact of a project refers to its ability to challenge and change existing societal structures and norms. Only co-managers assess shifts in attitudes, values, and behaviours related to the project's themes. Overall, the impact assessment serves as a tool for evaluating the multifaceted effects of projects, emphasizing the collaborative roles of both co-managers and co-participants in the assessment process across all impact areas. Thus, this evaluation framework ensures a thorough understanding of the project's impacts from multiple perspectives.

Table 3: Impact evaluation to summarise who should respond, what and when.

	Respondent	Ex-Ante	Ex-Post
Scientific Impact	co-managers	no	yes
	co-participants	no	yes
Social Impact	co-managers	no	yes
	co-participants	yes	yes
Economic Impact	co-managers	no	yes
	co-participants	no	yes
Political Impact	co-managers	yes	yes
	co-participants	yes	yes
Environmental Impact	co-managers	no	yes
	co-participants	yes	yes
Transformative Impact	co-managers	yes	yes
	co-participants	no	no

Figure 5. Recipe to measure the impact which is adapted in GREENGAGE from [8].

Finally, for the evaluation of the technology acceptance, the user’s satisfaction of the GREENGRAGE platform, the accessibility of the GREENGRAGE tools, the inclusivity of the GREENGRAGE solution, and the perceived usability of the GREENGRAGE platform, ex-post questionnaires were equally translated to foreign languages and then administered for both, co-managers and co-participants.

4.3 Alignment between CIM and the ACTION Methodologies

The CIM evaluation method and the ACTION methodology for impact assessment share strong conceptual alignment, yet each offers unique strengths. ACTION provides a structured framework with six clearly defined impact categories (scientific, social, economic, political, environmental, transformative), ensuring consistency and comparability across projects. These categories can be mapped directly to the ‘criteria’ (see appendix C) within the CIM method, while ACTION’s sub-categories correspond to CIM’s sub-criteria (see example in Figure 3). This mapping creates a coherent link between the two approaches, enabling integrated evaluation strategies.

Both methodologies rely on questionnaires as the primary tool for assessing impact. CIM offers flexibility by supporting both quantitative and qualitative questionnaires, allowing evaluators to capture nuanced insights and tailor assessments to project-specific needs. In contrast, ACTION predominantly uses Likert-scale questionnaires, which simplify participation and improve response rates but may limit the diversity and depth of feedback.

Stakeholder engagement is another area of distinction. ACTION emphasises identifying key stakeholders to ensure relevance and inclusivity in its evaluation process. CIM, however, goes further by enabling diversification of questionnaires based on project indicators, providing a mechanism to assess the degree to which objectives have been achieved. This adaptability is particularly valuable for complex projects where qualitative insights complement quantitative measures.

The flexibility of CIM in combining qualitative and quantitative approaches makes it well-suited for projects requiring customised evaluation frameworks. ACTION’s structured categories, on the other hand, offer clarity and ease of implementation, making it ideal for standardised assessments. The execution of ACTION and CIM methodologies is largely interchangeable, offering complementary strengths in impact assessment. While ACTION explicitly defines a structured process for both pre- and post-assessment, CIM adopts a more flexible approach that can be tailored to the specific needs of a project. This flexibility allows CIM to incorporate additional evaluation criteria and adapt its timing and scope based on project context, whereas ACTION provides clarity and consistency through its predefined stages. In practice, this means organisations can leverage ACTION’s systematic framework for standardised evaluations while using CIM’s adaptability to address unique project requirements or emerging indicators. Combining these approaches can result in a robust, comprehensive evaluation strategy that balances rigor with responsiveness.

The Figure 6 illustrates conceptual mapping between CIM and ACTION.

Figure 6: CIM and ACTION conceptual mapping

5 GREENGAGE CIM and Tools & Methods

According to the framework developed and described in sections 4 we analysed the list of objectives and impacts GREENGAGE aims to achieve. Within the Grant Agreement, KPIs (Key Performance Indicators) for outcomes and impacts are well defined. A selected list of KPIs is presented in Table 4 and full list is presented in Annex-B.

Table 4: The following table shows some of KPIs.⁴ (O is Outcome, I is Impact)

KPI ID	Outcome/ Impact	Description	Measurement
O1.KPI1	Outcome1	# of citizen observatories realized at each pilot	> 2/pilot
O1.KPI2	Outcome1	# of people involved in citizen observatories per pilot	> 250 / pilot
O1.KPI3	Outcome1	# of people from disadvantaged populations engaged per CO	> 80 / pilot
O1.KPI4	Outcome1	# of citizen observation experiments/interventions set up per pilot	> 2/pilot
I1.KPI1	Impact1	# of new or existing refined urban policies supported by GREENGAGE analytics workflows beyond the project lifetime	>=3
I1.KPI2	Impact1	# of business models for sustainability of GREEN Engine, toolbox, and thematic exploration data workflows	>=5

The defined outcomes and impacts are the indicators which have been assigned to Criteria and Sub-Criteria by using the CIM method. The Criteria can be related to the **Quality in Use**, and the **Product Quality** criteria from the ISO25010. The following Table 5 shows a subset of criteria for both groups, the entire extended list is in the Annex-C.

Table 5: A subset of criteria for Quality in Use and Product Quality.⁵

Criteria	Definition
Quality in Use (refers to system quality)	The quality in use of a system characterizes the impact that the product (system or software product) has on stakeholders. It is determined by the quality of the software, hardware and operating environment, and the characteristics of the users, tasks and social environment. All these factors contribute to the quality in use of the system.
Effectiveness	Accuracy and completeness with which users achieve specified goals
Efficiency	Resources expended in relation to the accuracy and completeness with which users achieve goals. Relevant resources can include time to complete the task (human resources), materials, or the financial cost of usage.

⁴ The entire list can be found in the Annex-B of this deliverable.

⁵ The entire list can be found in the Annex-C of this deliverable.

Satisfaction	Degree to which user needs are satisfied when a product or system is used in a specified context of use. For a user who does not directly interact with the product or system, only purpose accomplishment and trust are relevant. Satisfaction is the user's response to interaction with the product or system and includes attitudes towards use of the product.
Product quality (internal and external quality combined as product quality)	The product quality model can be applied to just a software product, or to a computer system that includes software, as most of the sub characteristics are relevant to both software and systems. The need for compliance with standards or regulations can be identified as part of requirements for a system, but these are outside the scope of the quality model.
Functional suitability	Degree to which a product or system provides functions that meet stated and implied needs when used under specified conditions. Functional suitability is only concerned with whether the functions meet stated and implied needs, not the functional specification.
Functional completeness	Degree to which the set of functions covers all the specified tasks and user objectives
Functional correctness	Degree to which a product or system provides the correct results with the needed degree of precision

This section presents the final status of the analyses. Discussions prolonged during the project and thus the framework was enhanced based on the perceived practices, challenges and lessons learned from the CO evaluations performed during the entire GREENGAGE project. The following Table 6 presents mapping of criteria, sub-criteria to indicators defined in the grant agreement.

Table 6: Criterion, Sub-criterion, Indicator matrix.

Criterion	Sub-criterion	Indicator
Effectiveness	Outreach and level of participation, Participatory Governance	Outcome 1: A more widespread citizen participation
Benefits, Effectiveness	Availability of new data for evidence-based decision making	Outcome 2: Greater availability of qualitative and quantitative in-situ data
Benefits, Effectiveness	Uptake of new data for evidence-based decision making	Outcome 3: Broader use of data and information collected by citizens
Benefits, Effectiveness	Uptake of GREENGAGE tools and methods	Outcome 4: Increased use of existing toolkits and development of new toolboxes (methodologies, methods, technologies) for broad use, which could include the development of efficient passive sampling systems observations;
Context Completeness, Efficient resource utilisation	Technological innovation	Outcome 5: Leveraged use of wearables for citizens and other low-cost technologies in the domain of environmental observation;

Participatory governance, Evidence based policy making and planning	Innovative governance	Impact 1: Innovative governance models enabling sustainability and resilience notably to achieve better informed decision-making processes, societal engagement, and innovation;
Qualitative benefits compared to pre-Greengage state	Technological innovation	Impact 2: Green Deal related domains benefit from further deployment and exploitation of Environmental Observation data and products;
Benefits	Contribution to GEOSS	Impact 3: A strengthened Global Earth Observation System of Systems (GEOSS)
Benefits	Sustainability and Competitiveness	Impact 4. Sustainability performance and competitiveness in the domains covered by Cluster 6 are enhanced through further deployment of digital and data technologies as key enablers
Knowledge Transfer	Awareness raising and citizen engagement	Impact 5. More informed and engaged stakeholders and end users including primary producers and consumers thanks to effective platforms such as Agriculture Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS)
Knowledge Transfer, Technological Innovation	Relevance to Sustainable Development Goals	Impact 6. Strengthened EU and international science-policy interfaces to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals

Each of the above indicators with description, questions, metrics, the evaluation methods, and tools are presented in section 5.3.

5.1 GREENGAGE Evaluation Process

As depicted in Figure 7, the GREENGAGE evaluation process has several stages:

- Design
- Co-Development and Co-Verification
- Implementation
- Reporting

Figure 7: GREENGAGE Evaluation Process

The depicted stages are explained below:

1) Design

This stage is used to prepare the evaluation objectives, scope and methods and tools. It consists of the following activities:

- a) Identification of the main set of criteria based on the requirements specification and GREENGAGE objectives.
- b) Deriving sub-criteria and identifying new indicators as well as re-using pre-defined indicators to achieve the objectives of the project.
- c) Deriving questionnaires to assess the outcomes.
- d) Specifying the methods and/or means to perform specific evaluation exercises to answer the evaluation questions.
- e) Identification of target groups taking part in the evaluation exercises.

2) Co-Development and Co-Verification

The purpose of this stage is to ensure that outcomes and impact indicators are appropriate for different stakeholders and are appropriately defined. The overall evaluation design was shared with project partners through workshops, to clarify and co-produce indicators and metrics. This stage results in:

- a) Verifying the evaluation design contents i.e., to clarify the semantics of specific terminologies used for criteria, indicators, metrics, methods, and questionnaire.
- b) Highlighting the importance of specific indicators and metrics.
- c) Indicating improvements in the indicators, target groups, questionnaire, metrics etc.
- d) Identification of additional criteria, indicators, questionnaire, and metrics.

3) Implementation

The actual evaluation was carried out as part of various WP6 tasks, and the following mechanisms have been applied:

- a) *In-system questionnaire*: These are generic questions to answer usability and benefit related aspects. This questionnaire has been provided through GREENGAGE's GREEN Engine (e.g., in Likert-scale form) so that whilst users using the GREEN Engine, can also evaluate them.
- b) *Online web-based or paper-based questionnaire in workshops/meetings*: These are specific questions to answer usability, benefits, and relevance aspects. There are two types of questions addressed: qualitative (open-ended) and quantitative (Likert-scale). For Likert-scale questions, the objective is to get qualified responses of the evaluation questionnaire for reasoning purpose and usage statistics for behaviour analytics. Such a qualified response helps to know why an evaluator responded to a certain question in a specific way that can help in deriving overall impact assessment and evaluation conclusions. Qualitative questions have been answered by groups of participants based on discussions and documented by GREENGAGE project team members. The team members acted as moderators for the discussion groups in order to elicit as many details as possible. For quantitative Likert-scale questions, we also provided additional fields to collect qualitative responses, which help in understanding the reasoning behind a specific answer. Both in-system and online web-based questionnaire have been customised to suit Pilot specific use cases. These questions are hosted on a professional survey platform. For the web-based questionnaires, various GDPR compliant platforms can be considered. For instance, EUSurvey, which is the official platform supported by the European Commission for hosting and running surveys or MS Forms through AIT's or UWE's MS Teams platform or Qualtrics survey or Google Forms by DEUSTO, which was used in the end.

- c) *Provenance data*: the aim here is to keep an anonymous log of different activities performed using GREEN Engine. This could be achieved by gathering anonymous platform usage logs for generating statistics about various required indicators e.g. registrations to GREEN Engine through website, number of times GREENGAGE Engine is used, time spent in the application, keyword searches, specific apps download in mobile phones, frequency of use, number of users in each user group, number of users responding to evaluation questionnaire, overall system rating, number of new datasets collected and deposited, number of data imports and exports, etc. However, to preserve privacy, limited statistics could be retrieved i.e., mainly from the evaluation surveys, registration web-page and the Greengage App.
- d) *Sentiment analysis*: As GREENGAGE collects a lot of qualitative data, for instance, audio conversations by using the Conversation Station. Sentiment analysis and/or opinion mining is used to understand participants' viewpoints.
- e) *Lessons learned*: As anticipated, several lessons are learned from applying the citizens observatories and evaluating the impacts. These are covered in detail in the GREENGAGE White Book D6.8.

4) Reporting

Results from the above stages, especially the implementation stage, provide a basis for further analysis. The evaluation implementation activities and results of evaluation have been reported in various WP6 deliverables:

- Task 6.2 results are documented in privacy impact assessment report (D6.3)
- Task 6.3 results are documented in the user evaluation report (D6.4).
- Task 6.4 results are documented in multiple impact assessment report (D6.5 and D6.6).
- T6.5 result are documented in White Book on lessons learned for public administrations (D6.7 and D6.8).

5.2 Workflow of the CIM development

The following examples shall elaborate the workflow used to develop the list of CIM as well as the tools to measure them, within the design stage of the evaluation process.

For the aimed **outcome** of GREENGAGE, ***A more widespread citizen participation*** the context related support questions are:

- Have the COs increased the participation of citizens in monitoring and protection of the environment?
- Could different gender (marginalized) groups be involved in data collections?

The **target groups** are all citizens with a special focus to:

- Civic associations (elderly, adults, neighbourhoods, grassroots, ecologist groups...),
- Engagement of women, marginalized groups, such as ethnic minorities, marginalized populations, and disabled persons.

The **metrics** related with this indicator are:

- # of citizen observatories⁶ **realized** at each pilot in GG.
- # people **involved** in citizen observatories per pilot.
- # people from **marginalized** populations engaged per CO.
- # citizen observation experiments/interventions set up per pilot.

As these metrics allow a huge range of interpretation (for example what are the semantics of **realized** and **involved**), we focus on the discussion to find useful definitions applicable for the different pilot areas. It turned out quickly that because of the greatly varying characteristics of the pilots, their use cases, and participatory processes, a one for all definition would not have made sense. However, the GREENGAGE glossary -established during the initial phase of the project- was used as a basis for describing the most important terms related to the CIM framework, the impact assessment and the user evaluation procedure.

A further step was then to find possible tools and methods to measure the metrics. For the above-mentioned metric “number of COs realized”, for example, it is important to look at the definition within the GREENGAGE glossary defining which elements and functions a CO should contain. Thus, in this context ‘*realized*’ means that community-based environmental monitoring and information systems which invite individuals to share observations, are established and working. Methods and tools in this context can be online registration forms, which also enable pilot owners to evaluate if marginalized groups are involved. What marginalized means is related to the context of the pilot area and topic, see also the glossary of this deliverable. Who is part of a marginalised group differing across situations. We need to identify the marginalised group for each CO. To identify them the following question can help:

- Who will be directly affected by the local policy innovations that we are aiming at but is usually underrepresented in participatory science & urban planning processes?

For the North Brabant pilot area, dealing with mobility issues, this means e.g., citizens with migratory background, parents taking children to places or people who live in mobility poverty. Similarly, for Gerace & Turano, older people are part of the marginalized group. For Bristol, people whose first language is not English, young people and children are part of the marginalized group.

The criteria this indicator refers to is **Effectiveness** with the sub-criterion **Participatory governance**.

The **target groups** are:

- Public administrations willing to explore the Citizen Observatories approach to open decision-making to citizens.
- Policymakers willing to validate newly deployed policies.
- Citizens willing to influence new Green Deal tackling urban policies.

Another example is related to the **impact** GREENGAGE is aiming for.

Impact can be defined as: “Wider long-term effects on society (including the environment), the economy and science, enabled by the outcomes of R&I investments (long term). It refers to the specific contribution of the project to the work programme expected impacts described in the destination. Impacts generally occur sometime after the end of the project, see also the glossary above.”

The corresponding **indicator** is:

⁶ Citizen Observatories (COs) are community-based environmental monitoring and information systems, that invite individuals to share observations, typically via mobile phone or the web. In GREENGAGE, COs oversee running Citizen Science (CS) campaigns to gain evidence for policy making. Notice that a CS campaign comprises a period when a group of Citizen Observers with a shared mission and hypothesis gather data at different places and regularly get together to analyse together the correlation of their collected data with other external data sources to validate such hypothesis --- from the GREENGAGE Glossary

- **Innovative governance models** enabling sustainability and resilience notably to achieve better informed decision-making processes, societal engagement, and innovation.

The context related support questions are here:

- Which new/innovative governance models can be supported by the GREENGAGE assets such as GREEN Engine?

The **metrics** related with this indicator are:

- # new or existing refined urban policies supported by GREENGAGE analytics workflows beyond the project lifetime
- # business models for sustainability of GREEN Engine, toolbox, and thematic exploration data workflows

The criteria this indicator refers to is **Participatory governance** with the sub-criterion **Innovative governance**.

5.3 Examples of Indicators

In this section we are presenting a few selected examples of outcomes and impact indicators. A full list of indicators is presented in the Annex-B.

Reference ID	GG_Eval_1000	Type	Outcome
Criteria	Effectiveness	Sub-Criteria	Outreach and level of participation, Participatory Governance
Indicator	A more widespread citizen participation	Version	1.0
Indicator Description	This indicator assesses the level of participation of citizens in monitoring and protection of the urban environment		
Metrics	# of citizen observatories realized at each pilot: (> 2/pilot) O1.KPI1 ⁷ # of people involved in citizen observatories per pilot: (> 250 / pilot) O1.KPI2 # of people from disadvantaged populations engaged per CO: (> 80 / pilot) O1.KPI3 # of citizen observation experiments/interventions set up per pilot (> 2/CO pilot site > 16) O1.KPI4		
Questions	- Have the COs increased the participation of citizens in monitoring and protection of environment? - Could different gender groups be involved in data collections?		
Target Groups	- Civic associations (elderly, adults, neighbourhoods, grassroots, ecologist groups), - Engagement of women, marginalized groups, such as ethnic minorities, disadvantaged populations, and disabled persons in co-creation efforts - Science museums, schools, civic and elderly people centres - Civil servants and policy makers		

⁷ O1.KPI1 ... stands for Outcome 1 Key Performance Indicator 1

Methods and Tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Maintaining a count of the number of citizens who showed interest in GREENGAGE piloting. - Maintaining a count of number of citizens who participated at any stage of the piloting activities including onboarding, workshops, emails, experiments, evaluations etc. - Maintaining a count of participants from diverse backgrounds through demographic analysis - Maintaining a count of number of experiments setup either through the GREENGAGE website or through in-system statistics - Maintaining a count of number of thematic co-explorations (use cases) for specific communities (or areas) initiated for each pilot <p>This can be done through in-system statistics of registrations or participation through in-person workshops, interviews, focused groups, the amount of thematic/use case related data captured, etc.</p>
Additional information	None

Reference ID	GG_Eval_1001	Type	Outcome
Criteria	Benefits, Effectiveness	Sub-Criteria	Availability of new data for evidence-based decision making
Indicator	Greater availability of qualitative and quantitative in-situ data	Version	1.0
Indicator Description	This indicator assesses the availability of qualitative and quantitative in-situ data for long time series and better geographical coverage, contributing to the in-situ component of existing observations.		
Metrics	# of new datasets crowdsourced and curated at each pilot: (> 4/pilot > 16) O2.KPI1 # of datasets contributed to existing observation systems: (> 3/pilot > 12) O2.KPI2 # of existing datasets harmonized with new evidence: (> 2 / pilot) O2.KPI3		
Questions	Could the CO increase the data availability?		
Target Groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Civic associations (elderly, neighbourhoods), already contributing with data - Civil servants and policy makers 		
Methods and Tools	This can be done by carrying out a survey with pilot owners/public administrations and other stakeholders including citizens to evaluate the value of new data in their decision making.		
Additional information	None		

Reference ID	GG_Eval_1002	Type	Outcome
Criteria	Benefits, Effectiveness	Sub-Criteria	Uptake of new data for evidence-based decision making
Indicator	Uptake or broader use of data and information collected by CO/CObs	Version	1.0

Indicator Description	Uptake of CO data and existing toolkits (e.g., GREEN Engine), and development of new toolboxes (methodologies, methods, technologies) for broad usage, which could include the development of efficient passive sampling systems observations.
Metrics	# of help provided in dealing new or existing urban policy challenges (with at least 2 per pilot). O3.KPI 1 # of experiments initiated and dealing with different issues. (0-4 use cases). O3.KPI 2 # of existing policies revisited with new evidence from citizen observations. (>1 per pilot) O3.KPI 3 # lessons and recommendations. (>= 5 per pilot) O3.KPI 4
Questions	- Is there and increase use of existing toolkits? - Is there increased use of data and info collected by citizens? - Is there an increased trust in data collected by citizens?
Target Groups	Citizen Observatory teams at each of the pilots' sites.
Methods and Tools	This can be done by carrying out interviews with Pilot Owners, a survey with COs and other stakeholders, and analysing the in-system statistics through GREEN ENGINE to evaluate the uptake of data, new thematic explorations, new sign ups and linking of GREEN Engine with new tools, etc.
Additional information	None

Reference ID	GG_Eval_1003	Type	Outcome
Criteria	Benefits, Effectiveness	Sub-Criteria	Uptake of GREENGAGE tools and methods
Indicator	Uptake or broader use of GREENGAGE tools and methods	Version	1.0
Indicator Description	Greater uptake of tools and technologies developed by GREENGAGE by pilots in setting up COs and engaging with citizens.		
Metrics	# of GREENGAGE tools being used by various COs in pilots. (>= 6). O4.KPI 1		
Questions	- Are GREENGAGE tools and technologies being used by various COs in pilots? - Are the tools and technologies helpful in the COs achieving their goals?		
Target Groups	- Pilot owners - CO teams at each pilot site - Citizens participating in the COs		
Methods and Tools	These metrics can be collected automatically by the GREENGAGE tools and technologies as well as through interviews with the CO teams.		
Additional information	None		

Reference ID	GG_Eval_1004	Type	Outcome
Criteria	Context Completeness, Efficient resource utilisation	Sub-Criteria	Technological Innovation

Indicator	Leveraged use of wearables for citizens and other low-cost technologies in the domain of environmental observation	Version	1.0
Indicator Description	The GREENGAGE tools and methodologies should make innovative use of existing tools and technologies to utilise existing resources sustainably and efficiently.		
Metrics	# of relevant existing technologies available at each CO. (>=1) # of relevant existing technologies utilised by GREENGAGE at each CO. (>=2)		
Questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Are there any existing tools and technologies that are relevant to the CO being set up at each pilot site? - Is GREENGAGE making effective use of any relevant tools and technologies that are available at each pilot site? 		
Target Groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pilot owners - CO teams at each pilot site. 		
Methods and Tools	This information can be collected from CO teams through interviews.		
Additional information	None		

Reference ID	GG_Eval_2000	Type	Impact
Criteria	Participatory governance, Evidence based policy making	Sub-Criteria	Innovative governance
Indicator	Innovative governance models enabling sustainability and resilience notably to achieve better informed decision-making processes, societal engagement, and innovation.	Version	1.0
Indicator Description	GREENGAGE CO approach and GREEN Engine will democratize Citizen Observatory activities (WP5) and will foster the sustainability of citizen observation experiments by enabling their replication and customization (WP4, 6, 7), either by the community contribution or by commercial services that could be hired through the GREEN Engine and offered by some of the SMEs of the consortium (SushiDev, DSR, MindEarth, GISAT, Moondial or HOPU).		
Metrics	# of new or existing refined urban policies supported by GREENGAGE analytics workflows beyond the project lifetime (>= 3) (I1.KPI 1) # of business models for sustainability of GREEN Engine, toolbox, and thematic exploration data workflows (>= 5) (I1.KPI 2)		
Questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Have GREENGAGE assets, such as GREEN Engine, resulted in innovative governance approaches? What are those new or improved governance approaches? - Have results from piloting resulted in policy validation, policy change or new policies? - Which new/innovative governance models can be supported by the GG assets, such as the GREEN Engine? 		
Target Groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public administrations willing to explore Citizen Observatories approach to open decision-making - Policymakers willing to validate newly deployed policies - Citizens willing to influence new Green Deal tackling urban policies 		

Methods and Tools	This will be done by identifying baseline governance models of Pilots and comparing them with possible improvements based on the results of COs followed by interviews with Pilot Owners and other stakeholders and a survey with COBs.
Additional information	None

Reference ID	GG_Eval_2001	Type	Impact
Criteria	Benefits, Evidence based urban planning	Sub-Criteria	Technological innovation
Indicator	Green Deal related domains benefit from further deployment and exploitation of Environmental Observation data and products;	Version	1.0
Indicator Description	Environmental observation carried by all and adapted to all will give place to better awareness, behaviour adaptation and empowerment of citizens to drive their city or region political decisions towards carbon neutrality.		
Metrics	# of areas of Green Deal dealt at project's pilots (≥ 4) (I2.KPI 1) # of datasets to policy workflows addressing Green Deal challenges (≥ 16) (I2.KPI 2)		
Questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Do piloting results indicate an awareness raising about environmental issues? - Do piloting results indicate behaviour change of COBs? - Do piloting results indicate that public authorities have more confidence in using CO data in policy making? - Do piloting results indicate new actions taken by public authorities towards carbon neutrality? - Do piloting results indicate new actions taken by COBs towards carbon neutrality? 		
Target Groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public administrations' departments promoting citizen observation and data-driven policies - Citizens concerned about the effects of global warming and willing to act to change this situation as Citizen science activists. 		
Methods and Tools	This will require determining an 'as-is' state of pilots either through situational screening (WP3/5) and/or conducting interviews or doing questionnaires with Pilot owners and relevant stakeholders or using/analysing existing data sets. This will be followed by regular monitoring during the piloting phase (e.g., analysis of the CO datasets to detect changes such as air quality, mobility mode shift, liveability etc.) and at the end to repeat the interviews and questionnaire to find out what has really changed.		
Additional information	None		

Reference ID	GG_Eval_2002	Type	Impact
Criteria	Benefits	Sub-Criteria	Contribution to GEOS

Indicator	A strengthened Global Earth Observation System of Systems (GEOSS)	Version	1.0
Indicator Description	By contributing new data and tools to the GEOSS system, GREENGAGE can help strengthen the overall system and make it more useful/effective/efficient.		
Metrics	# of tools contributing to GEOSS # In situ dataset contributed to GEOSS (>= 8) (I3.KPI 1)		
Questions	- Do GREENGAGE outputs help improve the GEOSS system? - Do GREENGAGE tools help make the GEOSS system more useful?		
Target Groups	Groups and communities that are part of and using the GEOSS system.		
Methods and Tools	This information can be acquired by surveying users of the GEOSS system and keeping track of mentioning of GEOSS in emerging literature.		
Additional information	None		

Reference ID	GG_Eval_2003	Type	Impact
Criteria	Benefits	Sub-Criteria	Sustainability and Competitiveness
Indicator	Sustainability performance and competitiveness in the domains covered by Cluster 6 are enhanced through further deployment of digital and data technologies as key enablers	Version	1.0
Indicator Description	GREENAGE outputs should help to improve sustainability performance and competitiveness in the domains covered by Cluster 6 (Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment).		
Metrics	# areas of Green Deal dealt at project's pilots (>= 4) (I2.KPI 1) # data to policy workflows addressing Green Deal challenges (>=16) (I2.KPI 2)		
Questions	- Are GREENGAGE outputs relevant to improving sustainability and competitiveness in domains covered by Cluster 6? - Do GREENGAGE outputs help address UN SDGs?		
Target Groups	- Pilots owners, - Domain experts, - GREENGAGE collaborators		
Methods and Tools	This can be ascertained through interviews with the pilot owners.		
Additional information	None		

Reference ID	GG_Eval_2004	Type	Impact
Criteria	Knowledge Transfer	Sub-Criteria	Awareness raising and citizen engagement

Indicator	More informed and engaged stakeholders and end users including primary producers and consumers thanks to effective platforms such as Agriculture Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS)	Version	1.0
Indicator Description	GREENGAGE outputs should help pilot owners collaborate with effective platforms such as AKIS to increase awareness and engagement with various stakeholders. The platforms can provide opportunities to co-create / recruit citizens in various CO initiatives.		
Metrics	# tools for data capture, curation and analytics integrated, published in ToolBox, documented and indexed in Academy (≥ 6) (I5.KPI 1) # lessons learnt and recommendations: (> 5 /pilot $\rightarrow > 20$ per project) (I5.KPI 2)		
Questions	How can GREENGAGE outputs be best used to engage with stakeholder groups?		
Target Groups	Pilot owners		
Methods and Tools	This information can be acquired through interviews with pilot owners		
Additional information	None		

6 Lessons Learned & Recommendations

In this deliverable we adapted the CIM method and designed criteria, indicators and metrics for GREENGAGE continuous evaluation. For impact assessment, ACTION methodology was adopted. The evaluation and impact assessment results have been documented in various other WP6 deliverables (D6.4 and D6.6).

Overall, we found it challenging to engage stakeholders in evaluation and impact assessment activities. This difficulty may be attributed to two main factors: the limited time stakeholders were able to volunteer and the lack of perceived relevance to the specific issues addressed by each observatory. Ensuring that evaluation activities align closely with stakeholders' priorities and context is essential to improve participation and the quality of feedback.

Based on the experiences of designing an evaluation methodology and its application, the following recommendations are made:

- *Ensure relevance:* The evaluation questionnaire must be tailored to the specific context and use cases of the pilots to be meaningful. Generic questions can quickly lead to disengagement and loss of interest among participants.
- *Tailor questions to specific stakeholder groups:* Ensure that the questionnaire is customised to reflect the roles, responsibilities, and perspectives of different stakeholders. Include questions on external influences (e.g., local policies, socio-economic conditions) that may affect the results. This approach improves relevance, engagement, and the quality of responses. For example, school children may require easy-to-understand language, technical stakeholders may require questions focused on system performance, while citizens may need questions addressing usability and satisfaction. Aligning questions with stakeholder priorities helps capture diverse insights and ensures that the evaluation reflects the full spectrum of project impact.
- *Prioritise and streamline:* Focus on the most important and time-sensitive criteria and questions to make the process realistic and efficient. Avoid including too many irrelevant questions, as this can be time-consuming and discourage volunteer participation.
- *Incentivisation for participation:* Evaluation is often perceived as a low-priority activity, even though participants commit significant time to data collection or experiments in citizen observatories. Because evaluation can be time-consuming, it is frequently overlooked or ignored. One effective way to increase engagement and ensure meaningful participation is to offer incentives. These could include recognition (e.g., certificates or acknowledgments), tangible rewards (e.g., vouchers or small gifts), or non-monetary benefits such as access to exclusive project insights or early results. Incentivizing participation not only improves response rates but also enhances the quality and reliability of the evaluation data collected.
- *Diversify collection methods:* Use both online mechanisms (e.g., surveys and in-app statistics) and alternative approaches (e.g., paper-based surveys) to maximise response rates and accommodate different participant preferences.
- *Pilot-test the questionnaire:* Conducting a pilot test with a small subset of participants greatly enhances the quality of the questionnaire by identifying confusing or irrelevant questions before full-scale deployment.
- *Creative engagement:* Make it easy and engaging for participants to share their feedback. For example, we could use colourful and/or uniquely shaped stickers (e.g., squares, circles, triangles or smiley faces) to let them express their feelings about specific questions on flipcharts. This hands-on approach is quick, fun, and works especially well when you have a large group at a project event.

Annex-A: Template for the Evaluation Design

The template is presented in Table 7.

Table 7: Template for the evaluation design for each Indicator.

Reference ID		Type	
Criteria		Sub-Criteria	
Indicator		Version	
Indicator Description			
Metrics			
Questions			
Target Groups			
Methods and Tools			
Additional information			

A full list of indicators in excel format provides a holistic view. The above template presents a simplistic view and was used to provide detailed description of each indicator.

Template Meta data:

Reference ID: A unique ID assigned to an indicator. For example, GG_Eval.

Type: Used to define the category of the indicator e.g., Outcome or performance, Impact etc.

Criteria: Main category to which the indicator belongs to.

Sub-Criteria: Sub-category of the main criteria to which the indicator belongs to.

Indicator: Brief title of the indicator.

Indicator Description: Covers detailed description of the indicator

Metrics: Lists the metrics associated with the indicator and will be used to determine progress towards achieving the objectives.

Questions: List of questions on what is involved. These questions are associated with indicators and metrics. Answers to these questions will help to determine progress towards achieving the objectives.

Target groups: Identifies who should be involved.

Methods and Tools: Identifies how metrics should be collected.

Additional Information: Any other information about indicators can be included. For example, responsible GREENGAGE partners for specific indicators can be included in this field.

Annex-B: List of current KPIs

The current list of KPIs which are metrics for various Indicators covered in section 5.3 is presented in Table 8.

Table 8: Entire List of KPIs

KPI ID	Outcome / Impact	Description	Measurement
O1.KPI1	Outcome1	# of citizen observatories realized at each pilot	> 2/pilot
O1.KPI2	Outcome1	# people involved in citizen observatories per pilot	> 250 / pilot
O1.KPI3	Outcome1	# people from disadvantaged populations engaged per CO	> 80 / pilot
O1.KPI4	Outcome1	# citizen observation experiments/interventions set up per pilot	> 2/pilot
O2.KP1	Outcome2	# new datasets crowdsourced and curated at each pilot:	> 4/pilot
O2.KPI2	Outcome2	# datasets contributed to existing observation systems	> 3/pilot
O2.KPI3	Outcome2	# existing datasets harmonized with new evidence	> 2 / pilot
O3.KP1	Outcome3	it is expected that citizen observations will help in dealing with at least 2 new or existing urban policy challenges per pilot.	>=2 input for new or existing urban policies / pilot
O3.KPI2	Outcome3	It is expected that for each pilot up to four use case experiments dealing with different issues will be initiated.	4 experiments / pilot
O3.KPI3	Outcome3	it is expected that at least two existing policies per pilot will be revisited with new evidence from citizen observations.	2 policies revisited / pilot ==> 8
O3.KPI4	Outcome3	It is expected that each pilot will result in at least 5 lessons and recommendations.	5 lessons learnt / pilot ==> 20
O4.KPI1	Outcome4	A number of reusable tools (>=6) will be made available (of which some might be open sourced in GitHub) as well as best practice use cases which enable to be used for data capture, curation and analytics (GREENGAGE Academy's catalogue).	>=6
O4.KPI2	Outcome4	Refers to the integration of the INTERLINK collaborative environment and Urban-TEP by DEUSTO (see 1.2.3 Related Research and Innovation).	1
O4.KPI3	Outcome4	For each pilot >=4 examples how the provided tools could be used for co-created urban analytics within different topics (thematic fields) will be made available in the GREENGAGE Co Academy e.g. as MOOCs	>= 4

O4.KPI4	Outcome4	Each pilot will hold at least one ad-hoc campaign (Datathon/summer school) to facilitate the testing and uptake of the provided tools.	1 ad-hoc campaign / pilot --> 4
O5.KPI1	Outcome5	it is expected that we have defined at least 4 interoperable adaptors or software APIs that integrate with off-the-shelf wearables. This requires us to integrate the captured data with the front-end for GREEN Engine to create a collaborative environment.	>= 4 interoperable adaptors or software APIs
O5.KPI2	Outcome5	it is expected that the data is harmonized between the data we capture via wearables and the authoritative data.	
O5.KPI3	Outcome5	it is expected that we will define at least 3 different applications where citizen scientists use wearables or portable sensors to gather in situ data that can be contextualized to provide micro-location data.	>= 3 different applications where citizen scientist use wearables or portable sensors to gather in-situ data
O5.KPI4	Outcome5	it is expected that Citizen Observatory teams are incentivized to use the wearables or portable sensors for periods of >4 hours due to the wearability of the devices and thus capture long term in situ data.	several over 4 hour long measurements
O5.KPI5	Outcome5	it is expected that we have at least five learnings which wearables or portable sensors have user interfaces and APIs that can be easily adapted.	>=4
I1.KPI1	Impact1	# new or existing refined urban policies supported by GREENGAGE analytics workflows beyond the project lifetime	>=3
I1.KPI2	Impact1	# business models for sustainability of GREEN Engine, toolbox, and thematic exploration data workflows	>=5
I2.KPI1	Impact2	# areas of Green Deal dealt at project's pilots	>=4
I2.KPI2	Impact2	# data to policy workflows addressing Green Deal challenges	>=16
I3.KPI1	Impact3	# In situ dataset contributed to GEOSS	>=8
I4.KPI1	Impact4	# New portable/low cost air quality sensor tested ready for commercialization	>=2
I4.KPI2	Impact4	# Urban analytics customization and consultancy services	>=4
I5.KPI1	Impact5	# tools for data capture, curation and analytics integrated, published in ToolBox, documented and indexed in Academy	>=6
I5.KPI2	Impact5	# lessons learnt and recommendations	> 5/pilot

Annex-C: List of Criteria and Sub-Criteria

Below we present a full list of criteria and sub-criteria based on the characteristics/sub-characteristics from ISO25010⁸, which will be adapted for the evaluation of GREENGAGE pilots. Please note that this full list may not be applicable for the evaluation and only selected criteria suitable for the GREENGAGE outcomes and impacts will be used. Further, the latest changes and new characteristics such as inclusivity from ISO205010:2023⁹ are also relevant for evaluation.

Quality in Use

Quality in use is the degree to which a product or system can be used by specific users to meet their needs to achieve specific goals with effectiveness, efficiency, freedom from risk and satisfaction in specific contexts of use.

Effectiveness, Efficiency, Satisfaction (Usefulness, Trust, Pleasure, Comfort), Context coverage (Context completeness, Flexibility).

The product quality model categorizes product (software or system) quality properties into eight characteristics and sub-characteristics.

Functional suitability (Functional completeness, Functional correctness, Functional appropriateness), Performance efficiency (Time behaviour, Resource utilisation, Capacity), Compatibility (Co-existence, Interoperability), Interaction Capability (Appropriateness recognizability, Learnability, Operability, User error protection, User engagement, Inclusivity, User assistance, Self-descriptiveness), Reliability (Faultlessness, Availability, Fault tolerance, Recoverability), Security (Confidentiality, Integrity, Non-repudiation, Accountability, Authenticity, Resistance), Maintainability (Modularity, Reusability, Analysability, Modifiability, Testability), Flexibility (Adaptability, Scalability, Installability, Replaceability), Safety (Operational constraint, Risk identification, Fail safe, Hazard warning, Safe integration).

Additional GREENGAGE specific criterion/sub-criterion

In addition to the above, we have identified other GREENGAGE specific criterion/sub-criteria presented in Table 9.

Table 9: Additional list of Criterion and Sub-Criterion

Benefits	Estimation of benefits by comparing ante and post GREENGAGE state of the tools and Applications. Both Relevance and Benefits can be partly related to effectiveness, efficiency, satisfaction, performance efficiency and context coverage characteristics of ISO 25010
Qualitative benefits compared to pre-GREENGAGE state	Determining any benefits to stakeholders and/or end users by using GREENGAGE tools and applications. For example, decision support, awareness raising, communication, quick feedback on proposals, analysis and visualisation using interactive platforms. Similarly, awareness raising, behavioural change, intervention, improvement and acceptance of planning

⁸ ISO/IEC 25010 – Online <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#iso:std:iso-iec:25010:ed-1:v1:en> last accessed 6 Jan 2024

⁹ ISO/IEC 25010:2023 - Online <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#iso:std:iso-iec:25010:ed-2:v1:en> last accessed 6 Jan 2024

	initiatives, information flow between community groups and local government, etc. are few other examples
Sustainability and Extensibility	Degree to which GREENGAGE tools and applications are reusable in different contexts and have the ability to be extensible by allowing to add new features
Technological innovation	Degree to which GREENGAGE technologies can generate new knowledge and innovative solution to environmental, social and governance problems
Participatory governance	Degree to which GREENGAGE supports participatory governance, e.g., how many users has the system attracted? How many additional users have got involved in the planning process because of GREENGAGE?
Evidence based urban planning	Ability to collect data evidence to support urban planning initiatives
Evidence based policy making	Ability to collect data evidence to support policy making
Evidence based decision making	Ability to collect data and public participation to support collaborative decision making
Provenance	Ability to trace evidence-based decision-making in planning applications and alternative proposals suggested by other users
Knowledge transfer	Ability to share knowledge and experience, awareness raising for behavioural change etc.
Efficient resource utilisation	Ability to make efficient use of resources (e.g., human resources, hardware, software etc)
Outreach and level of participation	Degree to which various users and stakeholders are approached and the degree to which number of participants increased or decreased
Availability of new data for evidence-based decision making	Degree to which new datasets are available and relevant to decision making processes
Uptake of tools and methods	Degree to which GREENGAGE tools and methods are adopted/adapted by Pilots or other public authorities or organisations
Innovative governance	Degree to which GREENGAGE resulted in changing the traditional governance approaches with the help of CO and innovative technologies
Contributions to GEOS	Degree to which GREENGAGE CO data contributes to GEOS initiative
Awareness raising and citizen engagement	Degree to which GREENGAGE tools and methods achieve increased awareness raising and citizen engagement in environmental initiatives
Relevance to EU Green Deal	Degree to which GREENGAGE piloting contributes towards different areas of EU Green Deal
Relevance to Sustainable Development Goals	Degree to which GREENGAGE tools, methods and piloting are relevant and contribute towards specific SDGs

References

- FP6 HUMBOLDT Project, (2011), European Commission, <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/30962>
- Deliverable A10.6-D1 (2010), – Scenario Evaluation Report, September 2010, FP6 HUMBOLDT project,
- Brooke J, (1996), SUS – A quick and dirty usability scale, In: Jordan P, Thomas B, Weerdmeester B (eds) Usability Evaluation in Industry, pp. 189–194, Taylor and Francis, 1996.
- Finstad K, (2010), The Usability Metric for User Experience, *Interacting with Computers*, 22(2010), pp. 232-327.
- ISO/IEC 25010:2011, (2011), Systems and Software Engineering – System and Software Quality Requirements and Evaluation (SQuaRE) – System and Software Quality model.
- ISO/IEC 25010 – Online <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#iso:std:iso-iec:25010:ed-1:v1:en> last Accessed: 22 Dezember 2025
- Kieslinger, B., Schaefer, T., Heigl, F., Dörler, D., Richter, A., & Bonn, A. (2018). Evaluating citizen science – Towards an open framework (S. 81–98).
- Ludlow, D., Khan, Z., Soomro, K., Marconcini, M., José, R. S., Malcorps, P., Lemper, M., Perez, J. L., & Metz, A. (2018). From top-down land use planning intelligence to bottom-up stakeholder engagement for smart cities - a case study: DECUMANUS service products. *International Journal of Services Technology and Management*. <https://www.inderscienceonline.com/doi/10.1504/IJSTM.2017.088949>
- Shapiro, J., 2007. *Monitoring and Evaluation Toolkit for Projects and Organizations*, CIVICUS - World Alliance for Citizen Participation. Belgium. Retrieved from <https://coilink.org/20.500.12592/w77xjk> on 22 Dec 2025. COI: [20.500.12592/w77xjk](https://coilink.org/20.500.12592/w77xjk)., last Accessed: 22 Dezember 2025
- Soomro, K, et. al., (2018), Deliverable 8.4 – Final Evaluation Report, Smarticipate Project, Horizon Europe. URL: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/693729/results> , last Accessed: 22 Dezember 2025
- Soomro, K., Khan, Z., & Ludlow, D. (2018). Participatory governance in smart cities: The urbanAPI case study. *International Journal of Services Technology and Management*. <https://www.inderscienceonline.com/doi/10.1504/IJSTM.2017.088945> , last Accessed: 22 Dezember 2025
- Venkatesh, V., M. G. Morris, G. B. Davis, and F. D. Davis. 2003. User Acceptance of Information Technology: Toward a Unified View. *MIS Quarterly* 27 (3): 425-478.
- Venkatesh, V., J. Y. Thong, and X. Xu. 2012. Consumer acceptance and use of information technology: extending the unified theory of acceptance and use of technology. *MIS quarterly* 36 (1): 157-178.